

Effects of bullying on school students in Saudi Arabia: a systematic literature review

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ABSTRACT: This study examines the effects of bullying on school students in Saudi Arabia through a systematic review of extant literature on the subject. Its scope includes the measures that have been taken to recognize, identify and tackle the issue, the reasons for its prevalence in Saudi school settings, and the psychological factors that facilitate victimization. The methodology is based on the use of quantitative and mixed research journal articles that deal with the various aspects of the phenomenon. The results reveal a prevalence of bullying, especially involving physical violence, against male students; females, in contrast, use more verbal and psychological violence towards each other.

Keywords: Bullying. Saudi Arabia. Schools. Abuse. Victimization

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1. Introduction

Bullying involves physical and/or psychological force or coercion, which is manifested as harassment, intimidation and abusive behavior toward a victim (Miller and Lowen, 2012). It typically consists of a repeated pattern of behavior with psychological consequences for the victim (Salmivalli, 2010). Bullying occurs in situations where there is an imbalance in the power dynamics between victim and abuser (Berger, 2014). This distinguishes it from other types of abuse. There is a hostile intention reinforced by the power imbalance that repeats over time (Miller and Lowen, 2012). The abuser intends to hurt the victim psychologically and/or physically. Bullying may happen person to person or within a group. The latter follows the lead of the main perpetrator, who provides it with support and feedback. Bullying can take place at work or in school, following the imposition of hierarchies that see the abuser as the dominant player and victim as the submissive one (Berger, 2014).

Significant implications arise from it, as the victim suffers anything from discomfort to profound injury as a result of the abusive behavior (Salmivalli, 2010). Bullying sometimes takes place as a result of the desire of the perpetrator to gain control over others (Solberg & Olweus, 2003). This gives rise to a bullying culture in which negative implications of hierarchical interactions become manifest in all spheres of life. Bullying can take place in family settings and within communities and neighborhoods. It can occur via social media (Solberg & Olweus, 2003) and in this form has become widespread among adolescents.

Bullying can be anticipated and predicted in situations where the person who perpetrates it has been encouraged by other bullies (Vanderbilt & Augustyn, 2010).

Four kinds of bullying have been identified. Psychological bullying often has significant emotive repercussions, generated by the relational dynamics between abuser and victim. Verbal bullying is often manifested in expressions of anger and hate directed toward the victim. Physical bullying occurs when there is force or coercion applied to the victim. Cyber bullying has recently become a significant phenomenon as a result of the rise of the Internet and social media. In many cases, abusers feel safer when perpetrating acts of verbal and psychological violence in a semi-anonymous environment. Bullying often singles out individuals because of differences in gender, race, body size or ability. Modern society facilitates its spread due to the high level of connectivity and interdependence that characterizes it (Salmivalli, 2010).

2. Bullying in schools in Saudi Arabia

Bullying has become widespread in Saudi Arabia in the last few years. It is estimated that around 50% of all students have been, at some point, victims of psychological and/or physical bullying (AlBuhairan et al, 2016). This has prompted national authorities to enact legislation that requires all educational institutions to check for instances of bullying. Saudi Arabia is implementing procedures aimed at ensuring that bullying is prevented and its pernicious effects tackled appropriately. The policies implemented have the support of bodies such as the National Family Safety Program and the Saudi National Childhood Commission. The Saudi government has followed recommendations from UNICEF and other international bodies when introducing legislation (AlBuhairan et al, 2016). The phenomenon of bullying in Saudi Arabia follows international trends, and has been aggravated by the presence of social media. It was found that the commonest type of bullying is of a verbal nature and that physical presence is an important prerequisite when trying to understand the phenomenon (Jambi, 2020).

An increase in the level of physical bullying has been found, possibly linked to growing exposure to violence through the Internet. Social bullying is not as prevalent (Olthof et al, 2011). This is perhaps explained by the fact that Saudi Arabia is a conservative country with strong religious values, which might deter the spread of bullying at a communal level. There is a clear indication that male students suffer more bullying than females, and that primary school students are more likely to be bullied than those at secondary and tertiary level (Georgiou & Stavrinides, 2008).

There is a tendency among Saudi students to tell teachers and other school authorities when they are being bullied (Johnson, 2009). At the same time, teachers are better educated in areas related to bullying and therefore in a better position to respond to incidents (Olthof et al, 2011). A practice instituted in Saudi Arabia's schools consists of creating a social environment in which bullying is not allowed to thrive. The trend is toward fostering a healthy interaction between students and to root out manifestations of violence among them. Teachers are instructed to intervene at an early stage and to analyze the state of affairs as it develops. However, there is still some ignorance as to what needs to be done at a comprehensive level, as seen in the fact that some practitioners choose to simplify and trivialize the phenomenon (Alsalem et al, 2021).

Contested Definitions and Prevalence Rates

One of the challenges in tackling bullying is that it is difficult to define. Bullying can be characterized as a form of aggressive behavior that has the intent of harming another person who is the unwilling recipient of the violence (McKee, 2018). The term is also associated with the identification of the way in which power is misused in the context of human interaction through consistent physical, emotional and psychological injury to others.

However, there are some discrepancies regarding the setting in which this takes place. Intent is a crucial aspect of bullying as well as the objective that is ascribed to it (Olthof et al, 2011). Additionally, any definition of bullying needs to take into account the timespan of effects caused by the phenomenon. The concept of bullying is related to the cultural and social setting in which it emerges. It is also important to consider that the very people who perpetrate bullying tend to have their own ideas on the subject (Sanders, 2004).

Bullying needs to be defined in the context of the educational setting. It occurs when one student victimizes another for no reason other than to inflict physical or psychological pain. The literature indicates that between approximately 10 and 40% of students are bullied worldwide (McEachern et al, 2005). The prevalence is informed by the particular cultural setting of each country. For instance, in Scandinavian countries, which traditionally have high levels of social trust and an anti-bullying culture, the fraction is approximately 15%. In the United Kingdom, the ratio is approximately 30% (McEachern et al, 2005). Internationally, bullying tends to be more pronounced between males than females. The latter tend to suffer more verbal abuse than males, who are more subject to physical violence (Georgiou & Stavrinides, 2008). There is an upward trend due to the proliferation of technology and the detrimental effects of exposure to violence. Students from racial and ethnic minorities tend to suffer more bullying than the rest (Olthof et al, 2011). The behavior of the students affected by bullying tends to change significantly as a result of the abuse. For example, students who are victimized tend to lose interest in school and in many cases suffer depression or anxiety.

Aims of the Review

The aim of this review is to advance knowledge on the implications of the incidence of bullying in Saudi Arabia's high school system. The main objective of is to determine the reasons for the prevalence of this phenomenon in the high school system, which has increased in magnitude in recent year. The review also aims to shed light on the fact that this phenomenon has not received as much attention and the potential solutions that can be brought forth in order to address the problem by the school authorities, the national government and parents.

3. Methodology

The methodological scheme adopted centers on the use of research databases such as the Saudi Digital Library, which holds theses and journal articles produced by students and researchers in Saudi Arabia. In addition, there was also extensive use of journal articles by Saudi authors. Additional material was accessed through the Education Resource Information Centre and use of electronic journal databases such as Google Scholar, addressing the research through terms such as "bullying in schools," "bullying," "effects of bullying," "school students," "discipline in schools," "child maltreatment," and "violence at schools."

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

The research undertaken used inclusion criteria based on scholarly literature related to the issue of bullying in schools in Saudi Arabia since the early 1990s. This includes journal articles, postgraduate theses and books on the subject. The inclusion criteria are based on research undertaken in order to tackle the issue of bullying at all levels of the school system. The exclusion criteria referred to unofficial research or that carried out by non-governmental organizations, material not published in English, and studies that do not focus on the issue of bullying or the protection of children and adolescents.

4. Results

A total of 10 studies from the literature on the effects of bullying on high school children were analyzed. Two studies were excluded. The results from the 10 studies are summarized in Table (1) according to research methodology. The studies were undertaken exclusively by Saudi researchers, so that there is less diversity of the literature and fewer different researchers involved than the number of studies might suggest.

Kazarian & Ammar (2013) state that the problem of bullying is quite prevalent in the Arab world, adding that, "while decades of empirical research on the understanding, assessment and prevention of school bullying exists in Western countries, interest in school bullying in the Arab world is a recent phenomenon [and that a] possible suggested factor in the relative delay of interest in school bullying relates to the absence of a specific Arabic term for bullying or difficulty in establishing a satisfactory Arabic equivalent to the English term "bully" because of dissatisfaction with such prevailing electronic Arabic-English dictionary translations as *baltagi*-hired thugs and *al irhabi*-terrorist" (p.1). Conceptual definitions are, therefore, important in understanding problems related to bullying in Saudi Arabia. The authors mention that the emergence of viable linguistic alternatives has been a factor of decisive importance in finding solutions for the problem.

The literature also addresses the psychological implications of bullying for schoolchildren. AlBuhairan et al (2016) identified three areas that need to be examined in detail with regard to bullying: the type of bullying that takes place in the high school system, the factors that inform the encouragement of bullying in that setting, and the implications of bullying for students. The authors point out that: "a lack of safe environments, recreational facilities, and inconsistencies in addressing problematic behaviors were subthemes that were found to be conducive to bullying, whereas dislike of school, racism, aggressiveness, and social isolation were emergent subthemes that were reflective of the potential impact of bullying" (p.64). The authors emphasize that the focus of attention needs to be on establishing preventative measures to address the problem of bullying in the high school system. In their cross-national study of the relationship between childhood bullying and addictive and anti-social behaviors among adults in Saudi Arabia, Almuneef et al (2017) state: "bullying victims [at school age]...are 1.8 times more likely to smoke, 2.3 times more likely to drink alcohol, 2.9 times more likely to use drugs, 2.1 times more likely to have ever had out of wedlock sexual relations, and 2.5 times more likely to have suicidal thoughts compared to those who were not bullied" (p.20170052). AlBuhairan et al (2017) state: "more males than females, and more older adolescents were exposed to bullying [and that] exposure to physical violence and bullying were both associated with higher odds of having more frequent symptoms of depression and anxiety [and that] those exposed to physical violence were at higher odds of having poorer academic performance" (p.61). Alrokban et al (2019) state identify a correlation between being bullied and bullying. They state: "victimization, seeking attention and being angry were the significant risk factors that control the occurrence of school bullying [raising] the awareness among school children about bullying and its consequence, encourage school administration to improve students' supervision in all school premises and deal with students' complaints seriously, and more studies are needed in Saudi Arabia targeting bullying in this age group" (p.105). Thus early intervention is crucial in tackling the problem.

Jambi (2020) states: "psychological ailment and symptoms of children involved in bullying tend to show increased symptoms of anxiety and depression, low self-esteem and poor social [and that] bully-victims are children who are involved in bullying both as bullies and as victims. (p.42). In their study on bullying in Khamis Mushait City, Alsaleem et al (2021) state: "more than half of the students tell teachers when other students are being bullied (53.7%) and tell a teacher or staff member at the school if they are being harassed (53.6%); teachers are doing anything they can to help if they are told that a student is being

bothered (58.7%), and teachers are making clear to students that bullying is not tolerated (52.3%)” (p.134). Sideridis & Alghamdi (2023) find:

“the presence of five profiles with levels of low, medium, and high bullying experiences, as well as two profiles with no cyberbullying experiences and medium high and medium low physical and verbal instances of bullying. Gender effects were highly pronounced, with most maladaptive bullying profiles being predominantly male. It is concluded that physical bullying is mainly occupied by males and the levels of cyberbullying are generally low in the elementary school grades. Implications for educational policy can clearly direct the development of support groups and expert counseling for both bullies and victims, staff training for identification and course of action, and the development of standardized school policies when such incidences occur” (p.610).

Table (1) Saudi studies on the effect of bullying in schools

N	Author and date	Study title	Nature of the publication	Research design	Sample size	Gender	Place of data collected	Area of study
1	Kazarian et al (2013).	School Bullying in the Arab World—A Review	The Arab Journal of Psychiatry	Literature review	None	Both	Across the Middle East, including Saudi Arabia.	Bullying
2	AlBuhairan et al (2016)	Bullying in Early Adolescence: An Exploratory Study in Saudi Arabia	International Journal of Pediatrics and Adolescent Medicine	Qualitative method	91 individuals: 40 students, 31 school professionals, 20 parents/caregivers	Both	Saudi Arabia	Bullying among adolescents
3	Albuhairan et al (2017)	The relationship of bullying and physical violence to mental health and academic performance	International Journal of Pediatrics and Adolescent Medicine	Cross-sectional national survey	9073 students	Both	Saudi Arabia	Mental and physical bullying
4	Alrokban et al (2019)	Bullying and its Risk Factors Among Elementary School children in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia	IRJPEH	Quantitative method	268 students: 123 boys, 145 girls	Both	Riyadh	Bullying risks factors
5	Jambi (2020)	Saudi Child Bullying in Primary Grades Schools: the Case of Jeddah, Saudi Arabia	International Journal of Sports Science and Arts	Mixed method	569 enrolled in general education grade schools	Both	Jeddah	Bullying in primary grades
6	Khasawneh (2020)	The Extent of Bullying Against Students with Learning Disabilities According to the Age Variable	International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research	Quantitative method	350 students with learning disabilities	Both	Saudi Arabia	Bullying of students with learning disabilities
7	Alsaleem et al (2021)	Bullying Prevalence among Secondary School Children in Khamis Mushait City	Behavioral Sciences	Quantitative method	300 students	Both	Saudi Arabia	Bullying risks factors
8	El Fatah et al (2022)	A Psychoeducational Intervention for Teachers about Bullying Behavior Prevention Among Secondary School Students	Middle East Current Psychiatry	Quantitative method	60 teachers	Both	Al Masra	Intervention to contain bullying
9	Sideridis & Alghamdi (2023).	Profiling Experiences of Bullying in the Elementary School	Children	Mixed method	3867 fourth graders	Both	Saudi Arabia	Bullying behavior in elementary schools in Saudi Arabia
10	Sideridis & Alghamdi (2023)	Bullying in Middle School	Children	Mixed method	5567 eighth graders	Both	Saudi Arabia	Bullying in schools

There is a need to ensure that a proper network of support is established to address the problems that stem from bullying. El Fatah et al (2022) state: “there is highly

statistical significance between total intervention regarding bullying at school and total bullying perceptions post-psychoeducational intervention [and that] It is important for teachers to receive a psychoeducational intervention from time to time to help them teach students how to solve their problems that can redirect potentially negative or passive behaviors to positive problem-solving and leadership skills” (p.1). The literature points to the fact that bullying is becoming more widespread for both genders across schools in the Middle East. Sideridis & Alghamdi (2023) state that in the Middle East: “levels of bullying across all domains were elevated in males compared to females, contrasting earlier views that different types of bullying are linked to males versus females” (p.873). It is therefore important to ensure that the authorities are able to establish mechanisms needed for creating the right network of support for victims and abusers. Khasawneh (2020) states: “awareness programs should be developed for teachers to help them identify indicators associated with bullying, in addition to future studies on the phenomenon and its relationship to other variables, such as social anxiety and emotional intelligence” (p.267). Important psychological implications arise from bullying that need to be addressed for the purpose of resolving this issue in the school system.

Nature of publications, research design and data collection tools

All the papers were published in peer-reviewed journals. Two of these journals are from the Middle East but have an international readership of significant importance and are of a high quality in terms of the impact of their content. One study used a cross-national survey, while another used a literature review. Five of the papers used a quantitative method of analysis. One used a qualitative approach. The rest used a mixed method, combining quantitative and qualitative research.

Sample size and gender

The studies used populations of hundreds or thousands of students/teachers across a range of cities in Saudi Arabia, and included males and females. Some significant differences were evident in the manner in which bullying affects males and females, the former being more likely to experience violence. Two of the studies show significant variations in the way in which both set of students are affected psychologically by this phenomenon. One of the studies focuses on the impact of bullying on students with learning disabilities.

Place of data collected and Study area

The data for the studies were collected from several places in Saudi Arabia, enabling a view of the way in which bullying affects male and female students from different regions. Surveys were also conducted among students and teachers from various elementary and secondary schools. One of the studies was conducted in Riyadh, another in Jeddah, which has a more liberal social outlook.

Findings of Saudi studies

The study by AlBuhairan et al (2016) found that bullying is facilitated by lack of a safe environment in which to undertake school and recreational activities. The authors found that unaddressed behavioral problems (such as aggression and isolation) were likely to result in actions leading to bullying. AlBuhairan et al (2017) found: “26% of adolescents reported exposure to bullying in the preceding 30 days, and one out of every three adolescents reported exposure to physical violence at school during the past year” (p.61). The study found out that exposure to bullying was more significant in males than female and that exposure to physical and psychological bullying was associated with a greater incidence of depression, anxiety and poor academic performance.

Almuneef et al (2017) state: “39% of participants” were bullied, although there were some significant differences in the type of bullying experienced. Men tended to report higher levels of physical violence, with 19% of them reporting sexual violence. Women were found to experience a higher level of psychological and social violence. In both cases, the incidence of bullying resulted in promiscuous and addictive tendencies (p. 20170052). Alrokban et al (2019) found in their study of elementary schools in Riyadh that more than 80 percent of students who were bullied reported the incident to their teachers, which could have positive effects in addressing long-term psychological implications of the problem. Alrokban et al (2019) found that those who perpetrated bullying tended to be victims themselves, particularly among the male population, with a marked tendency toward the use of physical and psychological violence. The study showed a strong correlation between being bullied and becoming a bully. It was found that the incidence of bullying was greater among older students. Alsaleem et al (2021) point out in their study on prevalence of bullying among secondary school children in Khamis Mushait City that the overall rate of bullying was about 65%, with a tendency toward wider use of verbal violence, rather than physical and social. Male students tended to suffer more than the female students. Those in lower classes were subject to abuse more than those in higher classes. El Fatah et al (2022) state that students who are bullied are likely to be victimized on an intermittent basis. Jambi (2020) points out in his study on the incidence of bullying in Jeddah elementary schools that most students were subject to verbal violence (13.2%), which in some cases (9.6%) led to physical violence and damage to property. There was also an exposure to social bullying which tended to impact negatively on the psychology of victims. The situation in Saudi Arabia is replicated in other parts of the Arab world. Kazarian & Ammar (2013) state: “the limited prevalence studies on school bullying in the Arab world suggest varying rates with 20.9% of middle-school adolescents reporting bullying in the United Arab Emirates, 31.9% in Morocco, 33.6% in Lebanon, 39.1% in Oman, and 44.2% in Jordan; boys typically endorsing more engagement in peer victimization than girls” (p.1). Sideridis & Alghamdi (2023) highlight the importance of gender in examining bullying. Approximately two thirds of female students in the elementary schools have not experienced bullying, compared to one third in the case of male students. Sideridis & Alghamdi (2023) state that males are likely to incite more traditional forms of bullying while female students may use relational manipulation. In this context, the aspect of socialization as it applies to gender has the potential to shed light on the manner in which the phenomenon unfolds.

Table (2) Findings of Saudi studies on bullying on school students.

N	Author and date	Types of bullying	Exposure (more than 2 events) incidence	Abuser	Consequences
1	Kazarian & Ammar (2013)	20.9% of middle-school adolescents reported bullying in the UAE, 31.9% Morocco, 33.6% Lebanon, 39.1% Oman, 44.2% Jordan	More than 30% of students across the Middle East	Students	More research needed in the Arab world concerning forms, signs, locations and consequences of school bullying
2	AlBuhairan et al, (2016)	Verbal, physical, sexual psychological/social, cyber	Widespread	Students	Problematic behavior Aggression Psychological damage
3	Albuhairan et al (2017)	24% physical	21%	Students	Low self esteem Anxiety Depression
4	Almuneef et al, (2017)	40% physical 19% sexual	59%	Students	95% more likely to use alcohol 95% more likely to smoke
5	Alrokban et al, (2019)	8.7% physical 1.6% verbal 3.6% verbal	10.3%	Students	Increase in level of anger among students

6	Jambi (2020)	13.2% physical 9.6% verbal	22.8%	Students	Low self esteem Depression Anxiety
7	Alsaleem et al, (2021)	Verbal, physical, relational, online	64%	Students	Psychological damage
8	El Fatah et al (2022)	13.2% verbal 12% social	25%	Students	Low self esteem Depression Anxiety Poor performance
9	Sideridis & Alghamdi (2023)	Physical Cyber Verbal	Elevated levels of bullying in males compared to females.	Students	More opportunities for early identification of bullying incidents
10	Sideridis & Alghamdi (2023)	Verbal, physical, relational, online	Both male and female students engage in bullying, with more males engaging in it.	Students	Low self esteem Depression Anxiety

5. Types of bullying

The studies indicate that bullying is manifested in various ways, affecting both male and female students. They point to a prevalence of physical bullying toward males, while female students are more likely to be affected by psychological and verbal aspects of the phenomenon. The school system in Saudi Arabia is affected by the same challenges faced in the Western world and elsewhere in the Middle East. The widespread use of technology creates opportunities for disrupting traditional school life. Use of the Internet and social media affords students who bully more opportunities to harass their victims. There is an indication that female students are subject to bullying by other female students, although not in the same proportion as males are by other males.

Prevalence

The prevalence of bullying in Saudi Arabia is significant, bearing in mind that the country has strong conservative social values. The use of physical, as well as psychological, sexual and verbal, bullying appears to be widespread. This has prompted the Saudi government to look at the issue comprehensively, due to the potential repercussions it could have on the psychological wellbeing of the population at a later stage. The studies also indicate that the prevalence of bullying in the school system could serve to explain the incidence of addiction and promiscuous behavior among the adult population. The fact that this phenomenon is extensive in the school system in Saudi Arabia also shows there need to be measures put in place to contain bullying, not just in the school environment but also in the home and communal setting.

The abuser

The studies show that the main perpetrators of bullying tend to be males, who direct their attention towards threatening classmates and intimidating victims physically and psychologically. Sometimes the abuser incites violence by spreading rumors or ridiculing their victims in a manner that makes them feel inferior. On other occasions the abuser issues threats in front of the teacher or directs attacks against him/her and other school personnel. This situation indicates the complexity of the psychology of the abuser and the way in which the problem concerning bullying needs to be tackled. The emphasis should be on creating awareness about the grave psychological damage that his/her behavior may have in order to safeguard other students and the class in general.

6. Consequences

The literature review shows that the incidence of bullying has significant repercussions on the psychological and performative aspects of male and female student victims. Students who reported the incidence of bullying have generally benefitted from early intervention by teachers, hence preventing the spread of the phenomenon and the negative impact it may have on students at a later stage. It appears that the Saudi authorities have a clear indication of measures that need to be taken in order to address this issue. Bullying needs to be addressed through preventative strategies aimed at containing the phenomenon before it becomes widespread in the school system. It is important to raise awareness about the consequences it can have for both male and female students.

7. Discussion

One of the main problems associated with bullying is that it may not be identified at the moment it happens. In many cases, incidents of bullying are not identified because the victim refuses to acknowledge or report it. In some situations, the victim is dissuaded from reporting because her/his psychological outlook may be too damaged to do so (AlBuhairan et al, 2016). This means that the literature has not been able to identify all the factors that impact on the dynamics of bullying. What we do know from the studies shown above is that in spite of the best efforts of researchers, bullying continues to be difficult to measure and define in a proper way. Although it is known that bullying includes emotional, verbal and physical abuse, it is not possible to measure in an exact way how this situation impacts on the long-term health of the victim (Sideridis & Alghamdi, 2023). Self-reporting is still the method most widely used among researchers to measure the incidence and consequences of bullying.

It appears that cyber bullying is a phenomenon that impacts women more strongly. There is a tendency among males to remain silent about bullying due to the social pressures placed on masculinity from an early age in Saudi Arabia. The studies indicate the need to establish psychological and emotional correlations regarding the intersection between bullying in the virtual and physical domains. While the two are closely related, the variables that inform the psychological consequences of bullying in both domains tend to be somewhat different (Albuhairan et al, 2017).

There is no objective way to measure the phenomenon, which has consequences when it comes to making decisions about the prevention of physical and psychological violence against victims. There is also the problem of anonymity in measuring the way in which bullying is studied. Furthermore, there is a quite marked variation in the frequency with which the bully exercises physical and psychological violence against victims. While bullying requires a certain consistency in terms of the time period in which the violence is exercised, there are periods of intermittency that must also be considered when measuring the frequency with which bullying is exercised (El Fatah et al, 2022).

The studies above yield important conclusions about the relational aspects of bullying. Victims of abuse tend to suffer a certain kind of social condemnation. Bullying affects not only their psychology but also their relationship with peers. In the case of females, bullying occurs slightly more intermittently, although this could also have much more severe long-term implications due to the more social and emotional nature of the victims. In the case of female students, their relational reputation tends to suffer in a more marked manner, hence expanding the degree of psychological damage generated by the bullying (Alrokban et al, 2019).

8. Finding's gaps

The studies indicate that in order to have a more comprehensive view of bullying in Saudi Arabia, it is necessary to undertake studies that have more qualitative than quantitative orientation. The methods used have tried to quantify the phenomenon and to highlight the variables that sustain it. However, in order to generate better prevention measures, it is necessary to take into account the information derived from the people who are impacted by bullying. This requires undertaking studies based on questionnaires and analyzed from a thematic perspective – something that is not yet common among Saudi researchers. It is also necessary to differentiate more strictly between the way in which the phenomenon of bullying impacts males and females, which requires a much more qualitative orientation and a move away from anonymity. All this could lead to a much more comprehensive view of the bullying in Saudi Arabia and to taking measures to improve the spectrum of prevention.

9. Conclusion

In conclusion, the literature review on the subject of bullying in the school system of Saudi Arabia shows there is a growing prevalence of male and female students affected by this phenomenon. The trend appears to be widespread across the country. The fact that the national authorities have reacted effectively offers promise in ensuring that male and female students are not affected psychologically by the implications generated by the use of coercion and intimidation. Another important element to bear in mind relates to the great extent of this phenomenon in Saudi Arabia, notwithstanding the fact that the country has strong conservative values. This state of affairs indicates that the country is being influenced by trends that come from the Western world and that are also affecting the Middle East school system. Furthermore, the influence of technology and the availability of violent material on the Internet are factors that explain the prevalence of this phenomenon and the need to root it out from Saudi Arabia's school system.

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